

IMPROVING THE PREVENTION OF ILLEGAL TRAFFICKING AND OTHER ACTIONS COMMITTED FOR THE PURPOSE OF TRAFFICKING NARCOTIC DRUGS OR PSYCHOTROPIC SUBSTANCES

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Abstract: This article analyzes research on improving the prevention of illegal trafficking and other acts committed for the purpose of trafficking narcotic drugs or psychotropic substances, and the author develops proposals and recommendations.

Keywords: drug addiction, psychotropic substances, prevention, illegal circulation.

The scale and rate of drug addiction spread in the world, as well as issues of ensuring the physical, moral, and spiritual health of people, are becoming one of the urgent problems. According to the 2024 UN World Drug Report, in 2022, one in every 18 people in the world aged 15 to 64 had used narcotic drugs or psychotropic substances in the last 12 months.[1] The global report indicates large revenues from the sale of narcotic drugs and psychotropic substances, social and economic problems such as poverty and unemployment, the growing demand for narcotic drugs and psychotropic substances in some countries, and the legalization of certain substances as the main reasons for the widespread use of these drugs and substances. According to the Central Asian Regional Information Coordination Center (CARICC), the number of crimes involving the illegal trafficking of narcotic drugs or psychotropic substances increased by 13.8% in Kazakhstan, 7.5% in Russia, 2.8% in Kyrgyzstan, and 1.6% in Tajikistan in 2024.

Therefore, it should be noted that the illicit trafficking of narcotic drugs and psychotropic substances is becoming a serious social and economic problem on a global scale. In particular, the illegal trafficking of narcotic drugs and psychotropic substances and actions committed for the purpose of their trafficking pose a serious threat not only to the healthcare system, but also to social stability. Therefore, it is very important to study advanced foreign experience in combating this problem, preventing it, and increasing its effectiveness.

If we consider the impact of the illegal circulation of narcotic drugs and psychotropic substances, then their illegal trade and sale lead to serious negative consequences in society. This poses a threat not only to the healthcare system, but also to security and social stability. Drug trafficking and illicit trafficking generate high crime rates and lead to an economic crisis. At the same time, the illegal trafficking of narcotic drugs and psychotropic substances jeopardizes social norms, spirituality, and the rule of law in society.

Several countries are implementing best practices in the prevention of illicit drug trafficking and crimes committed for the purpose of drug trafficking. In particular,

The Dutch government has implemented a very harmonious and systematic approach to drug trafficking. They focused on reducing drug use, controlling drug distribution, and rehabilitating users. Legally, the Netherlands has created social programs aimed at the provision of drugs under relaxed laws and the rehabilitation of users[2].

The Swedish government is known for its strict drug policy. In Sweden, measures have been taken to prevent illegal drug trafficking, such as public education, protecting young

people from bad habits, and promoting a healthy lifestyle. Another important aspect is that decisions are made based on scientific research and statistical data to increase the effectiveness of preventive programs conducted in the country[3].

Singapore has the strictest laws regarding drug-related crimes. The government of Singapore has implemented a strong preventive and punitive policy aimed at the complete eradication of drug addiction. A high level of legal literacy of the population and legal education on drugs serve as an important factor in the fight against drug trafficking and transfer[4].

In our country, systematic measures are being implemented to combat the illicit trafficking of narcotic drugs or psychotropic substances, prevent these crimes, and eliminate their consequences. In particular, the "National Strategy for Combating Drug Addiction and Drug Crimes in the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2024-2028," approved by the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. UP-73 dated May 6, 2024, defines the tasks of developing research activities in the field of combating drug crimes, implementing scientific research, conclusions, achievements and innovations in this area, as well as developing proposals for improving legislation and law enforcement practice in this area and their implementation. In this regard, a number of measures are being implemented aimed at further improving the scientific and theoretical foundations for improving the prevention of illicit trafficking and other actions committed for the purpose of trafficking in narcotic drugs, psychotropic substances or their analogues in the current criminal legislation. However, there is a need to make preventive programs more effective in this regard.

Therefore, to improve the prevention of crimes committed for the illegal sale and sale of narcotic drugs, the following proposals can be implemented:

Firstly, increasing the population's knowledge about drugs, conducting large-scale awareness-raising work to protect young people from harmful habits;

Secondly, the implementation of comprehensive programs to combat drugs by ensuring the joint work of governmental and non-governmental organizations;

Thirdly, the use of modern monitoring systems to prevent drug trafficking, such as the use of special sensors and intelligence technologies;

Fourthly, in the fight against drug addiction, the creation of special programs for the rehabilitation of victims and their return to society.

Studying advanced foreign experience in combating the illicit trafficking of narcotic drugs and psychotropic substances will serve as an important resource for further improving Uzbekistan's own prevention system. At the same time, the effectiveness of the fight against drug addiction can be increased through the joint work of the state and civil society, the strengthening of socio-educational programs, and the application of new technologies.

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